

STRUCTURE, ELEMENTS, TYPE AND TYPES OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL EDUCATION

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Annotation:

the structure of training, elements of training, type of training, type of training, teaching method, thematic planning of training are mentioned.

Keywords: educational process, lesson, structure of training , elements of training, type of training, types of training, thematic planning.

Introduction

Modern education is a complex network of institutions, programs and methods aimed at implementing the educational process and developing the knowledge and skills of students. It plays an important role in the development of society, in the preparation of a new generation of specialists who can work successfully in modern conditions.

The structure of education includes basic elements such as levels and stages of education, educational institutions and their components, as well as the content and organization of the educational process. Each level of education (primary, basic, secondary, higher) has its own characteristics and requirements aimed at developing students, broadening their outlook and forming various competencies.

The type of education depends on the purpose and direction of education. Thus, formal education is carried out in educational institutions with the issuance of officially recognized and obtained documents (schools, universities, etc.). Non-formal education includes various courses,

trainings, seminars held outside the formal education system to improve skills and acquire new knowledge or skills. And finally, unstructured learning is the direct acquisition of knowledge and experience from the environment, self-education.

Modern education is also characterized by the diversity of educational programs and methods. These include traditional lectures, practical exercises, laboratory work, project assignments, distance learning and online courses. In order to increase the effectiveness of education, modern technologies and interactive methods are actively introduced into the educational process.

Modern types of modern education include ordinary schools, lyceums, gymnasiums, colleges, technical schools, universities, as well as vocational courses, language schools, online platforms and many other educational institutions. Each of these types of education has its own characteristics and goals, and is designed taking into account the needs and interests of students.

It can be seen in all aspects of education, while information technologies and pedagogical technologies occupy one of the most important places in ensuring the final results of the development of educational technologies in the continuous education system. Therefore, the use of information and materials of information technology as much as possible in the pedagogical technologies used in the education of the young generation is becoming an urgent issue of today, its development shows in every aspect of the development of the society.

The structure of the lesson should be very clear when it goes from one part to another, depending on its logic, the laws of the teaching process and the didactic purpose of the lesson.

The structure of training

1.	The structure of the process of acquiring new knowledge	Motivation - actualization of basic knowledge - reception - understanding and preliminary analysis - mastering check - consolidation - analysis.
2.	The logic of the process of consolidation of knowledge	Motivation - actualization of knowledge of the ends of action and pain - perception of the pattern of application of knowledge - independent application of knowledge in similar and new situations - self-control - control - correction - analysis.
3.	Logic of the process of complex application of knowledge and action points	Motivation - actualization of complex knowledge - example of complex application of knowledge - independent application of knowledge in similar and new situations - self-control - control - correction - analysis.
4.	The logic of the systematization and generalization process of knowledge	Motivation - analysis of the content of the educational material - separation of connections - systematization and generalization - establishment of inter-disciplinary and inter-disciplinary connections - worldview ideas - self-control - control - correction - analysis.
5.	Action points, evaluation and correction of knowledge, logic	Motivation - independent performance of control tasks - self-control - control - evaluation - analysis -

	of the verification process.	correction - reflection.
6.	An important criterion of training quality	The application of one or another type of work is not only the fact that the learners have been trained, but also that the purpose of the training has been achieved.

The structure of the training session is its total elements, which ensure the integrity of the training, as well as support the performance of active activities in different options. The components of the training are closely related and are carried out in a specific sequence. The structure of the training depends on the goal, the content of the material to be studied, the methods and methods of teaching, the level of training and development of the learners, and the place of the training in the educational process. Each type of training has its own structure with its specific elements. As an example, let's take the most common elements.

Structural elements of training

Bocchich	Didactic tasks	Real indicators of the results of solving tasks.
Organizing the beginning of the training	Training students to work in training.	Complete preparation of the room and equipment, quick involvement of learners in the rhythm of work.
Check if homework is done	Establish accuracy and awareness of homework completion by all learners.	Add control and cross-check optimality to establish correctness of tasks and correction of defects.
Preparation for the first part of the training	Providing learning activities and motivation received by learners, actualization of basic knowledge and skills.	Preparation of students for active educational activities in basic knowledge acoc.
Acquisition of new knowledge and action points	Provision of knowledge transfer and action points, acceptance and understanding, interaction and communication in the object of study.	Active movement of learners with the object of study, maximum use of independence in gaining knowledge and acquiring action points.
Dactlabki check of understanding of knowledge	To establish that the new educational material has been mastered correctly and consciously, to identify deficiencies, and to make corrections.	Mastering the essence of acquired knowledge and action points at the reproductive level.
Consolidation of knowledge and action	To ensure the assimilation of new knowledge and methods of action in	Independent performance of tasks that require the application of

points	changing situations.	knowledge in familiar and changing situations.
Systematization and generalization of knowledge	Forming the integrity of the system of academic knowledge on the subject, curc, distinguishing the ideas of the worldview.	Active and productive activity of learners on identifying connections between subjects and courses, entering classification.
Knowledge control and verification	Acquiring knowledge and actions, ensuring their correction, determining the level of quality.	Obtain accurate information about the achievement of planned learning outcomes by all learners.
End of training	Analysis and assessment of successful achievement of the goal, determination of future work.	Self-assessment of the learner, similarities with the teacher's assessment. Getting information about the specific result of education by learners.
Reflection.	Motivating students to reflect on their own behavior (motivation, action points, generalization). Mastering the principles of cooperation and self-regulation.	Gaps in learners' understanding and evaluation of their own actions. Forecasting of cooperative and self-regulatory nodes.
Information about homework, instruction on how to do it.	Ensuring understanding of the purpose, content, homework. Check Moc records.	Implementation of the necessary and sufficient conditions for the active development of all learners to successfully complete their homework .

Sample training structure.

1. Organizing the beginning of the training: setting educational, educational and developmental tasks, informing about the subject and plan of the training.

2. Essential knowledge (revision): checking the existing knowledge and skills of learners to prepare for learning a new topic.

3. Explaining new material: introducing new knowledge and skills, showing their reference examples.

4. Consolidation: acquisition of knowledge and skills by example and exercises on consolidation.

5. Concluding the lesson: forming summaries.

The type and types of training are highlighted in the table below.

Type and types of training

<i>Types of training</i>	<i>Types of training</i>
Access to training (learning and mastering new educational material).	Lecture, explanation, conversation, demonstration, research-type activity.

Summarizing training (training on systematization and generalization of knowledge, formation of knowledge and skills on the application of acquired knowledge). Consolidation and improvement of knowledge, skills and abilities.	Repetition, generalization, reproductive type training, practical training, excursion training, seminar, conference, final training, summarizing independent works.
Supervision (obtaining and evaluating knowledge and skills).	Competition, evaluation, competition, exhibition, competition.
Combined.	This includes all 4 types of exercise training.

The laws of the holistic teaching process and the composition of the modern content of education, including mastery, determine a number of variable requirements for training, which are important.

The training includes not only the presentation of the materials, but also the tasks, which imply the practical application of the acquired knowledge. Part of this knowledge is obtained by the students in the process of independent research, by finding ways to solve the tasks, the presentation of the materials in the training should be varied. It can be ready information, solving a problematic task, proving a solution.

Training is a complex form of organizing the educational process, which requires a great responsibility from the pedagogue in the process of training, a creative approach to its planning: the correct distribution of time, control of each part of the training in the work of learners, personal training activities.

One of the most important requirements for the training is its scientific nature: training of students who are able to meet the requirements of the state educational standards; ensuring high camaraderie of the teaching process for the comprehensive and harmonious development of the learner's personality; use of the most appropriate teaching methods, forms and methods, as well as new educational technologies; formation of professional knowledge and skills in students, preparing them to use the acquired knowledge in practical activities; organization and control of their independent work; participation in the development of educational programs, quality training of graduates, taking responsibility for their full implementation in accordance with the schedule and curriculum of the educational process; observe the freedom and rights of learners; support the discipline of the educational system, control the order of participation in training; to follow the implementation of the curriculum and educational plans, to ensure compliance with the requirements of occupational safety during the educational process; conducting auxiliary work; to study the personal qualities of students, to communicate with their parents; to improve their professional skills.

For each academic year, there should be a calendar-thematic planner and study notebook. The thematic planning diagram is given in the appendix (training plan-concept).

Thematic planning chart

The name of the training type. Name of the learner. Duration, time, place of training. Age of learners and year of study. Teacher's qualification, category and pedagogy.	
Title of the subject	Acocan to the calendar-thematic plan
The training was successful.	Educational goal: refers to what knowledge, skills and competences the learners acquire. Developmental purpose: how the training can produce a developmental result. Educational purpose: what qualities of personality are formed.
Teaching methods.	Demonstration, conversation, training, etudes, improvisation.
Teaching forms.	Group, link, individual.
Type of training.	Macalan: combined, introductory training (learning new material) or final training (generalizing).
Equipment and resource information.	Acociy maxcuc literature, technical vocitas of teaching.
Training progress. In this, its teaching steps and sequence are defined, the necessary time is allocated for each step, the content of the steps, the work forms of the pedagogue and the learner, and the use of teaching methods and methods are determined.	
Repetition (repetition of learned material)	Here, what concepts and actions learned earlier should be activated, forms of work control are shown.
Learning new material, forming new skills and competencies.	New concepts and actions introduced on a given topic are shown. The expected progress in knowledge, skills and competences of learners is shown. It clearly shows what learners need to know and master, what actions to take and how to do it. Organization of control. In the process of learning new material, it is necessary to organize control over the assimilation of new knowledge, which includes: posing logical questions, feedback, independent work.
Consolidation of the learned material.	Skills and abilities must be strengthened in training, especially in the process of independent application. The types and types of independent work of learners are determined. Methodology of organizing independent work. This simple-to-complex principle is organized in 4 steps. 1. By sample. 2. Multi-independent (for example, in sync with the teacher). 3. Abcolyut is independent. 4. Creativity.
End of session.	Homework assignment.

Thus, the training structure mentioned above is implemented in the practical activity of the pedagogue with the help of the methodical structure. The methodical structure is determined by the

pedagogue, he chooses the voice, the point and the way. In doing so, he takes into account all the structures of the training and tries to implement them using a methodical structure. All the elements of the above-mentioned structure are as obvious as the practical tasks that the pedagogue should solve during the preparation and conducting of the training.

In general, the collection of tasks that make up the structure of training are as follows: organizational task, homework check, updating the learner's experience of the subject, learning new knowledge and methods of activity, pre-checking the understanding of what has been learned, consolidation, application, systematization and generalization, control and self-control, correction, information about homework, completion of the training session, reflection. From this collection of questions, the teacher creates many different combinations for the tasks to be solved in the training.

Acociy bocqich determines the type of training session. The following sequence is used within the scope of learning the subject: learning, repetition and consolidation of new knowledge, application of knowledge and skills, generalization and systematization, knowledge control and evaluation, and knowledge correction (correction) exercises.

Thus, the modern educational structure is a complex system of elements and methods that is improved over time. It develops students and prepares them to participate in a modern society of knowledge and skills.

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